

USE OF ICT IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AS A PEDAGOGICAL TOOL

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Abstract: Information and communication technology (ICT) advancements have opened up new opportunities for restructuring language learning and teaching environments. Today's language teachers and students face both fresh possibilities and challenges brought on by ICT as a pedagogical tool. The objective of this research is to look at teachers' competency in the utilisation of ICT as a pedagogical tool in English Language Teaching, i.e. ELT. Their competencies will be determined by their skills in computers, access to internet service and use of online software for teaching, assessment and feedback. The methodology adopted for this research is a descriptive-analytical survey with a sample size of 100 (25 men and 75 women) from various schools in Tashkent and Andijan regions in both public and private schools. Data was collected via convenience sampling via a questionnaire in Google forms circulated on 'Telegram'. The result found that most of the teaching staff is not very proficient in using computers and productivity tools on a basic level in ELT, and also they lacked knowledge on how to create interactive online courses and online teaching techniques. While few of the instructors utilised ICTs to research for the purpose of preparing English language lesson material, they did not actively integrate it into their practice as a means of instruction due to various challenges.

Keywords: English Language Teaching, ICT, Pedagogical Tool, Teachers' Competency.

1. Introduction

"Information and communication technology (ICT)" advancements have opened up new opportunities for restructuring language learning and instruction environments. Today's language instructors and students face both fresh opportunities and challenges brought on by ICT. The responsibility for conducting learning activities has shifted to the pupils, substantially altering the obligations of teachers. However, it should be stressed that teachers of modern languages, not ICT, determine the quality of the process of learning. This paper aims to provide information on the potential of ICT as a beneficial instrument for foreign language instruction and its implications for second language acquisition. (Yusuf, 2005)

ICT is now becoming much more popular in the teaching and study of foreign languages as more educators use it. ICT clearly has an influence on both the amount and quality of teaching-learning activities. Through its dynamic, interactive, and interesting material, ICT can specifically improve teaching and learning. It may also provide effective options for personalised training (Alkamel, 2018). "Information and communication technology (ICT) is regarded as one of the fundamental pillars of contemporary civilisation," according to (Daniels 2002). Understanding ICT and mastering its foundational skills and ideas are now widely regarded as essential components of education in many nations (Daniel, 2002). Utilising ICT in classrooms promotes student-centred learning settings. . Nonetheless, as the world rapidly converts to digital media and information, the importance of ICT in education will only grow throughout the twenty-first century (Ul- Amin, 2013).

Today, integrating ICT into the teaching and learning process is crucial. The teaching-learning process is anticipated to be both conventional and contemporary by the instructor. The teacher has to be ready to be able to use ICT in the pedagogical structure. "Although interactive,

language classroom technology is still underutilised in the twenty-first century” (Raya, 2014). It follows that both the quantity and quality of teaching and learning in conventional and distant learning institutions have been influenced by ICT. ICT may thus improve education by offering chances for personalised learning via its dynamic and interactive content (Vithal, 2015). Web-based learning also referred to as technology-based learning, virtual learning, online education, and e-learning, is one of the most rapidly expanding industries. It provides opportunities to create e-learning environments that are very well-designed, learner-centred, affordable, interactive, official, and customisable (Gomathi, 2016).

2. Objective

1. To look at enhancing teachers’ competency by the utilisation of ICT as a pedagogical device in ELT in Uzbekistan.
2. To look at the challenges being experienced by the teachers in using ICT as a pedagogical tool in ELT.

3. Methods

This study employs a descriptive-analytical survey approach to examine ICT capabilities as a teaching tool among ELT teachers.

Sample

The teacher’s sample consists of 100 people from Tashkent and Andijan region. Through the use of questionnaires, the data were gathered. A survey was conducted online. Participants who had an internet connection and were subscribers of the Telegram groups created by the researcher were carefully selected using convenience sampling. On Telegram, in-service student teachers’ forums, teacher groups forums, and school institution management groups from Tashkent and Andijan were chosen to participate in the poll.

Collection of data

A questionnaire is a tool composed of a number of uniform questions used to gather information from respondents on their computer abilities, access to internet service, and usage of online software for evaluation and feedback. In this respect, a Google Form was used to generate an online survey that was sent to the chosen Telegram groups for participation. In addition, some formal and informal discussion was also done with the selected sample.

Data analysis

In the study, descriptive analysis was used to assess the percentage and frequency of the general population in the demographic context using Microsoft Excel. Through the compilation of frequencies, tables, percentages, and tabulations, the data was analysed.

Demographic variables

AGE

Figure 1: Gender-related demographic information for responders

Working experience

Figure 2: Demographic information regarding respondents' employment experience

Analysis

The study sought information on respondents' real abilities as well as where and at what level they had learned ICT as part of the criteria for evaluating teaching competencies in this field. It is explored from a formal and informal discussion that few instructors, both male and female, learned ICTs via formal training, according to the data. Few respondents said they learned when completing their first teacher training, whereas few respondents said they learned ICT while advancing their academic credentials from diploma to degree. Other ways teachers learned ICT included their own initiatives through workshops and short courses. ICT workshops outside of schools, online communities or websites like YouTube, school-based CPD on ICT by an experienced or knowledgeable teacher and school-based CPD on ICT by experts from outside the school. Few people learned the skills by using their smartphones and self-education. This clearly shows the need for formal education, and the use of ICT is very important.

Presentation and Analysis of Results on Access for Learning, Teaching or Training Purposes for ELT.

Figure 3: Perception of teachers towards ICT as a pedagogical tool in teaching the English language

As shown visually in Figure 3, most of the respondents agree that the use of ICT helps in increasing their knowledge and skills. In addition, it is also explored that most of the teachers feel that ICT as a pedagogical tool is found to be a more powerful tool than traditional lectures and discussion in teaching the English language.

Usage and Challenges of Using ICT as a Pedagogical Tool in ELT

Figure 4: Usage and Challenges of Using ICT as a Pedagogical Tool in ELT

Most of the female respondents who provided information said they do not utilise ICTs at all while interacting with students in the classroom. Most of the respondents said they did not use ICTs in their interactions with others. The vast majority of respondents said they use ICT to interact with

students in the classroom. Most of the female respondents, including male respondents, said they never utilise presentation software in the classroom. In addition to this, most of those surveyed said they want to utilise presentation software with their pupils. For research, downloading, sending assignments, and other tasks, respondents want to utilise the Internet. In addition to this, the two main arguments put out for why most of the respondents did not utilise an LMS in their teaching. Most of the respondents found it very challenging to use ICT as a pedagogical tool.

Challenges in using ICT in teaching the English language.

Figure 5: Challenges in using ICT in teaching the English language.

Moreover, the majority of teachers are unable to utilise ICT in ELT. The above figure shows that various institutions did not have the capability and that they lacked ICT proficiency. Most of the respondents, including men and women, did not utilise ICT. Along with this, respondents said they do not utilise instructional software and thus are not able to use ICT as a pedagogical tool in teaching the English language. In addition to explaining the advantages of using ICT for educational purposes in the classroom, it is crucial, based on the aforementioned findings, to train teachers on the effective utilisation of the associated low-cost instruments. This will allow them to utilise technology to its fullest extent to improve and complement their training.

4. Results and discussion

The evaluation’s goal was to ascertain instructors’ ICT proficiency levels in English language teaching. The evaluation found that some of the teaching staff were proficient in using computers and productivity tools on a basic level, but they lacked knowledge of how to create interactive online courses and online teaching techniques. Although few instructors used ICTs to conduct studies for the purpose of producing lesson materials, they did not actively incorporate ICTs into their practice as a mode of instruction. In this regard, it is vital to train them so that they can effectively utilise the existing instructional infrastructure.

5. Conclusion

As a result of an increase in the number of teachers who use it, ICT is now enjoying a meteoric rise in popularity in the field of teaching and learning foreign languages. Without a doubt, the usage of ICT influences both the quantity and quality of learning and teaching activities. ICT has the potential to particularly enhance both learning and teaching by providing content that is dynamic, interactive, and fascinating. Additionally, it may provide efficient opportunities for individualised instruction, as researched by Alkamel (2018). According to Daniels (2002), “information and communication technology (ICT)” is one of the primary pillars of contemporary civilisation. In many nations, understanding of “information and communication technology (ICT)”, as well as mastery of its fundamental skills and concepts, are increasingly regarded as essential educational components.

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